

Data Management Plan (version 2025.1)

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Data Management Plan (DMP) characterises the existing and planned data management, data security, data access and policies within the MULTISOURCE project.

It describes the context in which research data will be created, its format and how it will be processed and stored before being archived for reuse on a longer term.

The DMP is a dynamic document and will be updated during the project. Horizon 2020 recommends creating new versions whenever there are significant changes in the project, such as new research data, strategic changes, or changes in external factors.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The overall goal of MULTISOURCE is to, together with local, national, and international stakeholders, demonstrate a variety of about Enhanced Natural Treatment Solutions (ENTS) treating a wide range of urban waters and to develop innovative tools, methods, and business models that support citywide planning and long-term operations and maintenance of nature-based solutions for water treatment, storage, and reuse in urban areas worldwide. MULTISOURCE will allow users to identify multiple sources for local water reuse, promote increased uptake of nature-based solutions, and minimize discharge of water that has not received adequate treatment. MULTISOURCE will deliver new knowledge about ENTS and their ability to remove waterborne contaminants and provide effective risk reduction for chemical and biological hazards, as well as their capacity to be integrated into the landscape and contribute to the improvement of urban habitats. The project includes seven pilots treating a wide range of urban waters. Two individual municipalities (Girona, Spain; Oslo, Norway), two metropolitan municipalities (Lyon, France; Milan, Italy), and international partners in Brazil, Vietnam, and the USA will contribute to each of the main project activities: ENTS pilots, risk assessment, business models, technology selection, and the MULTISOURCE Planning Platform. The use of urban archetypes in the Planning Platform will enable users to quickly classify regions (in both developed or developing countries) suitable for the application of nature-based solutions for water treatment (NBSWT) and compare scenarios both with and without NBSWT. This unique approach provides the knowledge, business models, and modular tools that will enable stakeholders to conduct fit-to-purpose, large-scale planning in their local region and, in doing so, promote circularity and sustainable development in the urban water sector and overcome barriers to widespread uptake of nature based solutions for water treatment.

2.0 MULTISOURCE data management practice

The data management will be handled using a decentralized approach. Each partner will be in charge of their own data collection, reconciliation and storage, but the Data Management Team (DMT) will oversee all aspects of data management over the course of the project. The DMT includes staff from the project coordinator INRAE and WP4 and WP5 leaders (ICRA and UFZ). The DMT’s mission is to: (i) write, oversee, and implement the Data Management Plan, (ii) define and share the meta-data formats that will be common to all partners, and (iii) centralize the curation of the metadata / data and their dissemination. As shown in Figure 2.1, data management is included upstream in the data lifecycle so that metadata production is included in the data post-processing workflow.

Figure 2.1 MULTISOURCE Data Management Process

3.0 MAIN SECTION

3.1 Data summary

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The core dataset of the MULTISOURCE project will consist in data collected from ENTS pilots (WP1). It will be associated with the data collected and produced in the risk assessment work package (WP2) and the business models work package (WP3). The data will support the development of a technology selection tool (WP4) and a planning platform (WP5).

What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

A significant amount of data will be generated by pilot monitoring (WP1) and consist in discrete and continuous monitoring of physical and chemical parameters. Raw data will be saved as plain text data but will be organized as hierarchical files for data exchange. A similar approach will be adopted for data of WP2 and WP3. In addition to data collected in WP1, WP2, and WP3, WP4 will collect literature data by data mining. WP4 will improve an existing online selection tool that produce output in csv format. In WP5, spatial data (raster and vector) will be collected and serve as an input for the planning tool that produce output in spatial data format (NETCDF, geotiff, geopackage). Table 3.1 lists the main datasets that will be produced within the course of the project, their sources and their purposes.

Table 3.1 MULTISOURCE data types

Data type	Format (s)	Used in work package	Source and used methods/tools	Purpose(s)
Bibliographic data	pdf, bib, enl	all workpackages	academic repositories	Gather information on previous studies
ENTS pilot protocol database	txt, docx, md	WP1	existing protocols (normalized or published), in-house development	share protocols among partners, associate to data for publication
ENTS pilot result database	Proprietary formats from instruments, xlsx, csv, db	WP1	(i) continuous measurements from online sensors, (ii) generated in-house through chemical analysis of samples	reporting and to feed into models being developed
NBSWT ontology	owl	WP4	developed upon existing ontology in the literature	developed an unified and hierarchical description of NBS associated data and create a standard for data exchange

NBSWT performance & design database	csv, json, db	WP4	existing SNAPP database and data mining	feed into models
NBSWT selection tool	software	WP4	source code	model core
selection tool simulations	csv, json	WP4	technology selection tool results	results obtained from the technology selection tool
Spatial data (roads, sewers, water infrastructure, ...)	vector data (shp, wms, wfs), raster data	WP5	Municipalities & open-data sources (e.g. OSM)	modelling of archetypes, multisource planning tool Infrastructure costs (investment, operation & maintenance)
Urban archetypes	vector data (shp, wms, wfs), raster data, model	WP5	analysis, aggregation and modeling	modelling of archetypes, multisource planning tool Infrastructure costs (investment, operation & maintenance)
NBSWT planning tool	software	WP5	source code	model core
planning tool simulations	vector data (shp, wms, wfs), raster data	WP5	Planning platform results	results obtained from the planning platform
Life cycle analysis database	Proprietary formats, csv	WP4	third party database, estimation based on partner information	LCA indicator will be incorporated into the NBSWT selection tool
ENTS Pilot stakeholder engagement mapping	pdf, xlsx, doc	WP6	Google Forms and Online sharing platforms (Miro board)	The mapping of the stakeholders supports the ENTS Pilots to have targeted interaction to receive feedback on the Pilot Results, Share key outcomes

<p>ENTS Pilot stakeholder engagement monitoring</p>	<p>xlsx</p>	<p>WP6</p>	<p>Google Forms and report</p>	<p>The monitoring of the stakeholder engagement will support to extract the lessons learnt and improve the stakeholder engagement processes in the upcoming activities.</p>
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Appendix 2 provides a list of datasets that are accessible in the [MULTISOURCE Zenodo community](#) upon the conclusion of the project.

Will you re-use existing data and how?

Pre-existing data consist in existing database (csv) like the one of the SNAPP tool (<https://snapp.icra.cat/>) and data collected from grey and academic literature using various procedure including data mining. Spatial data will also be collected from the project partners (sewer network) and online public databases (digital elevation model).

What is the origin of the data?

Five main sources of information can be identified: (1) literature review (grey and academic); (2) data and metadata from partners (research and city partners); (3) new empirical data; (4) public national and EU data servers; (5) simulation data WP4 and WP5.

What is the expected size of the data?

Data produced by sample analysis represent a limited volume of data (<10 MB). For the sake of comparison, an INRAE database that stores the results of the chemical analysis of more than 3,000 samples has a size of 9 MB. Time series associated to continuous monitoring of ENTS pilots will be in the range of 100 MB to 1 GB. The largest storage volume consumption will be associated to the spatial data used for WP5. This volume is expected to not exceed 1 TB.

All members of the research consortium are in charge of making sure that data are saved with sufficient precaution.

To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?

The data will be valuable for the following potential end-users: urban planners, consultants, entrepreneurs, authorities and researchers.

3.2 FAIR Data

3.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

A structured data storage is essential for proper and secure storage of data files and records. Therefore, each member of the multisource consortium is encouraged to maintain a file-based storage that includes clear and unambiguous file naming, the use of proper versioning and clear and intuitive folder structure. The Data Management Plan provides a template to achieve this goal as well as a suggestion for file naming that should also ease data exchange among partners. The recommended general naming convention for MULTISOURCE is as follows:

Naming: [MULTISOURCE]_[work package & task No]_[File name]_[Version No].[File format]

A template of folder organization for file storage is depicted in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1 Hierarchical folder structure for shared and archived files

Raw data files must be csv for tabular data and for spatial data (NETCDF, geotiff, geopackage). Data exchange among partners will be done through FTP, cloud folder access (SharePoint), direct accesses to database or API.

All public datasets will be uploaded to MULTISOURCE community in Zenodo, which will be peer-reviewed before acceptance to ensure the FAIR principles. For this purpose, a curation policy is provided in the Zenodo's community indicating the naming convention and the metadata fields to be filled up in a readme.txt, using the Dublin core as a reference.

One notable aspect of the project is that the samples collected on ENTS pilots are processed by various partners participating in WP1 and WP2. Consequently, it is essential to establish a quality assurance tool to monitor these samples. This was achieved by creating an Excel spreadsheet with a unified format, complete with standardized labels and vocabulary. Developed at the project's outset, this tool was presented at the first annual meeting. Special care was taken to ensure an easy transition from this format to one that aligns with FAIR principles. To this end, site, sample, and analysis keys were incorporated, allowing each Excel tab to be exported independently as a CSV file, while also enabling subsequent data merging between these files.

3.2.2 Making data openly accessible

All data produced within the framework of the project will be made openly accessible after completion of the tasks in the MULTISOURCE community in Zenodo. A six month delay between the completion of a publishable dataset and its public release should be the standard for the project. For reasons of competitive advantages, a data embargo may apply, including the completion of a PhD thesis, in which case an embargo of three years will be upheld. It is up to the partner to decide which data repository will be used for the publication of the results. Finally, special conditions may apply to the different software that will be developed. A stable version of the source code will be accessible using MULTISOURCE community in Zenodo and, optionally, in public VCS repositories. The development versions are organized in institutions' VCS: a dedicated GitLab in INRAE and UFZ and ICRA's GitHub account.

3.2.3 Making data interoperable

Data interoperability will be enforced by: (i) proper folder organization, file naming and open format, (ii) utilizing a standardized data exchange format that is based on the [TW data exchange format](#)¹, and (iii) the systematic usage of metadata.

3.2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

The data will be licensed following the Creative Commons licenses CCO or CC BY and by adding machine readable licenses. Software developed within MULTISOURCE will be made available under GNU's General Public License or MIT license.

3.2.5 Allocation of resources

The process of making the data meeting FAIR principles was already anticipated with the definition of the data management task of the WP8. There are no expected costs for data storage in the institutional repositories more than the person hours dedicated to prepare and upload the data, which had been already included in the dedication in person month of each partner to the different WP. In addition, person months have been allocated for the redaction of the data management plan and of the development of companion documents and tools, namely notes on good data management practices and on the usage of the sharing tools, and centralized inventory of samples and metadata.

3.2.6 Data security

Each partner is responsible for their data storage, which depends on routines in operation under institutional policies.

¹ This format is an outcome of Sophie Guillaume's PhD thesis, crafted using the thesaurus and ontology she created during her doctoral studies, sponsored by MULTISOURCE.

3.2.7 Ethical aspects

Ethical issues have low potential impact on data sharing in MULTISOURCE. However, since some partners will collect and process data obtained during interviews and workshops that include personal details, consent forms will be provided and stored adequately by the partner in charge of those activities. Furthermore, all personal data will be properly anonymized before making it public.

APPENDIX 1: METADATA README FILE

This annex describes the list of the metadata fields that must be provided with raw data in a companion readme file. This list is based on the DUBLIN core.

- **Title:** Name given to the resource: the title is usually the formal name by which the resource is known.
- **Creator:** The entity primarily responsible for creating the content of the resource.
- **Subject:** The topic of the resource content. Generally, the topic is expressed in the form of keywords or phrases
- **Description:** A presentation of the content of the resource. Examples of descriptions include: abstract, table of contents, reference to a graphical representation of the content, free-text presentation of the content.
- **Publisher:** The entity responsible for making the resource available or disseminating it.
- **Contributor:** An entity responsible for contributions to the content of the resource. Examples of contributors include an individual, organization, or department.
- **Date:** Date of an event in the life cycle of the resource. This will usually be the date the resource was created or made available.
- **Type:** Nature of the resource. At least one Type element conforms to the DCMI Type Vocabulary which includes 12 values: collection, dataset, event, image, interactive resource, moving image, physical object, service, software, sound, still image, text. (<http://dublincore.org/documents/dcmi-type-vocabulary/>)
- **Format:** The physical or digital manifestation of the resource. The values for this element, for the description of a digital resource, come from the list of MIME (Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions) types maintained by The Internet Corporation for Assigned Names and Numbers. (<http://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/>)
- **Identifier:** Unambiguous reference to the resource in a given context. (DOI)
- **Source:** Reference to a resource from which the described resource is derived.
- **Language:** The language of the resource
- **Relation:** Reference to a related resource.
- **Coverage:** Perimeter or scope of the resource's content, i.e., the spatial and temporal coverage of the resource. It is recommended that a value be selected from a controlled vocabulary (e.g., the TGN Thesaurus of Geographic Names) and that, where appropriate, place or period names be used rather than numeric identifiers such as coordinates or date ranges. (http://www.getty.edu/research/conducting_research/vocabularies/tgn/)
- **Rights:** rights associated with the resource.

APPENDIX 2: LIST OF DATASETS AVAILABLE ON ZENODO MULTISOURCE COMMUNITY

NAME	CONTENT	DOI
Risk assessment of pilots – D.2.3	Four excel spreadsheets containing concentrations, risk quotients and risk reduction. Those data support deliverable D2.3 which also contains sample codes for data processing.	10.5281/zenodo.15526428
Results of the Analysis Campaign for the ICRA Pilot Green Wall under the MULTISOURCE Project	Contains csv files with the results of the measurements carried out on the ICRA Pilot Green Wall	10.5281/zenodo.15525354
MULTISOURCE Deliverable D5.5. Results of scenarios for the MULTISOURCE municipalities	This repository contains the modeling results of the urban stormwater management scenarios presented in deliverable D5.5	10.5281/zenodo.15425128
Water samples REFLET Rhizosph'air 2024	This repository contains four files containing data collected from the Rhizosph'air pilot operated by INRAE	10.5281/zenodo.15488753
NIVA sample inventory & data transfer – MULTISOURCE		10.5281/zenodo.15374854
Microplastics sensor data – MULTISOURCE	Raw data of the turbidity sensors installed at the inlet and outlet of the Norwegian pilot	10.5281/zenodo.15374917
PRA model specification for all pilots	A complete model specification for all pilots derived from HUGIN software	10.5281/zenodo.15117633
Knowledge base for NBS for water treatment and stormwater management	The database used to build the snapp tool	10.5281/zenodo.13885202
Water samples UFZ green roof research 2022-2023	This repository contains four files containing data collected from the Green Roof Research pilots operated by UFZ within the framework of the MULTISOURCE project. More details are provided in the README.txt	10.5281/zenodo.15497678
Dataset from Merone CSO-CW (Italy)	This dataset was collected as part of the monitoring activities carried out during the MULTISOURCE project on a full-scale aerated hybrid treatment wetland located in Merone, Italy.	10.5281/zenodo.15606285
Influent & Effluent concentrations of aerated hybrid wetland (Phytoparking): conventional parameters, pathogens & OMP	The Phytoparking systems have a first VSSF stage, followed by a HSSF stage. 13 water samples were taken over the course of 2 years and analyzed at University of Ghent or sent to Aarhus University in Denmark or the Norwegian Institute for Water Research in	10.5281/zenodo.15584720

	Oslo, Norway. More information on the system can be found in https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2024.105603	
Water samples_Bridger Bowl Treatment Wetland_2023	This repository contains four csv files containing data collected from the Bridger Bowl pilot operated by Montana State University within the framework of the MULTISOURCE project.	10.5281/zenodo.15388493

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